

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY LEARNERS OF ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE**Alaviyya N.,***Lecturer of the chair "English and methods"*ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4219-1071>**Babayev J.***The senior lecturer of the chair "English and methods"*ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-2472-0006>*Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10381536>**Abstract**

The article elaborates the main problems emerged in the process of language acquisition. The first challenge may be illiterate or unqualified teacher who demotivates the students in the lesson process. Another problem may be lack of teaching resources which reduces the quality of learning. Sometimes, teacher domination may be the biggest obstacle in learning a foreign language. Age may sometimes become a matter in language learning. Improper use of language learning methodology can also impede the effective language acquisition.

Keywords: acquisition, method, challenge, teaching aids, student-centered education

Studying a second language is not an easy task. Acquiring English as a second language is even more difficult particularly when you learn English in a country whose official language is not English. For instance, English language learners in African countries like Zimbabwe, Malawi, Madagascar, Somalia, Angola, Algeria and some other African countries encounter a number of challenges as English is not the mother tongue of most of these countries. The official languages of African countries are predominantly classified as English, French, Arabic and Portuguese. North part of Africa speaks Arabic while the rest of the continent speaks mainly English and French. Though English is the official language of some countries in Africa, some local languages are also spoken by indigenous people. Dialects spoken in the countries whose official language is English are quite hard to understand.

The English language learners may face the challenges shown below:

1. Unqualified teacher

This is the most vital and overlooked issue. What makes this problem so complicated to solve is that since most communities contain English language learners, they are not able to ascertain who is a proficient English teacher and who is unskilled. Whatever the teacher teaches, either being wrong or right, will be accepted as correct by the students. This brought about a great deal of confusion among the students because diverse teachers tell them various things. One of the main reasons of this matter is the hardship that the teachers own while translating or interpreting from their mother tongues into the target language. For instance, the word "tub" is articulated by different teachers as either [tab], [tob] or with a vowel which is absent in English. The sound [ʌ] is not present in the sound systems of most African languages, so even the teachers sometimes experience challenges while pronouncing it.

2. Restricted learning atmosphere

While saying limited learning atmosphere, we don't mean weather. We mention the presence of furniture at the lesson or location of education institution.

Since all these factors may have an impact on the learning process, especially in learning English what takes place outside of the classroom matters most. In most cases, the learners make an effort to speak correct English at the lesson when they are under supervision. Besides, they don't hear people converse correct English. As a result, it is more complicated to learn proper English.

3. Lack of aiding devices.

Learning materials pertain to items which have a contribution in the process of learning. Books can be considered to be an essential material, but books are not sufficient by themselves [10]. Besides, audio devices are also important during the lesson. When a learner sees a sound symbol somewhere, he/she does not know exactly how to pronounce it without hearing the correct pronunciation by a native speaker. It means that the students learn something haphazardly. They own the books to read but they don't know how the words are pronounced exactly. It would be difficult for a student to know how to pronounce the word 'ewe' The student should hear the correct pronunciation from his/her teacher or from a native speaker of English in order to retain in mind correctly. Students are prone to acquire the language from films that they watch but they often learn the inappropriate things because films contain slang and dialects which are not valid in academic form of communication.

4. The students consider their lessons frivolous

In the meantime, students often presume that English which they use at home or in the street is the identical they will have to employ in their examinations. Nevertheless, as interaction doesn't need to be grammatically proper in order to be intelligible, students don't always follow the rules that they studied at school and, for this reason, they do not get completely educated and pass their exams successfully.

Therefore, the learners don't learn the English language and they study other disciplines. In many case, the students learn the language only during the lesson when the teacher teaches English. Once the lesson is over, they put their books aside and wait for the next

lesson. They don't study pronunciation, they don't study essay writing, and they don't make an attempt to learn new words. They disturb the teacher with small problems during the lessons, even with the words that they could just look up in the dictionary. They don't want to tire themselves when they want to know the meaning of a word. They always ask the teachers instead of looking the new words up in the dictionary. When learners make mistakes and they are corrected, they often claim "It is not my language after all." This too much self-confidence insignificantly impacts their ability to learn English.

Despite of the presence of qualified teachers, relevant materials and exposure to native speakers, we will still see a myriad of problems which any ESL student will face. One of these problems is the overuse of the mother tongue during the class.

5. Over-usage of native language in the lesson process

The students can assimilate another language profoundly when they are urged to use it. Instructors ought to be ready to require the learners to communicate in English and only in English even when they converse to each other. If you know the students' mother tongue, pretend as if you are unaware of the language because that will urge them to ask and respond to the questions in English. This problem sources from the cultural needs of the society and family. But there are some controversial ideas about the usage of mother tongue. Babayev Javid underlines the importance of usage mother tongue in learning a foreign language: "It means that while explaining or comparing native and target languages, a language learner masters the language understandingly and grasps the language profoundly. So it is very crucial to use the mother tongue in language learning process" [1, p.51].

6. Too much dependence on the teacher in the class

Integral part of learning something means the realization of how to solve the challenges on your own. If the students address the teacher with a small matter that she/he experiences, then the learner won't be able to learn the language on her/his own. When the learners insist that they are unaware how to say or do something on their own, they will be convinced that they can do that with inspiration and positive impact [6].

7. Domination of the lesson by strong students

It makes no difference how well the learners are selected, there will still be differences in how they know and how quickly they are able to learn. Keeping up with the accomplished students will leave the weaker ones behind. The latter should not be isolated in different classroom activities and discussions.

8. Wrong choice in methods of learning a foreign language.

Some students and teachers choose wrong methods while learning and teaching a second language. Some teachers prefer applying traditional methods which are effective for some students while ineffective for others [3]. Though GTM is an outdated method of teaching a foreign language, it can still be an effective method [4] though listening skill cannot be developed properly through this method [7]. CLT is considered to

be the most ideal foreign language teaching method compared to other methods [8]. It has some effective techniques which make the students acquire the language profoundly [5]. It has also some key strategies and tips in teaching the foreign language through CLT which have been elaborated in author's article [9, p.124]

9. The role of age.

Age can be a matter in learning a foreign language. As we know, aged people can comprehend an acquire the language harder than the juveniles. However, it depends on a person. This feature may change individually [2]

There are numerous steps that can be taken to develop English language skills for the learners who are willing to try their best:

1. They ought to be very attentive to make sure to utilize relevant materials recommended by a professional English instructor.

2. They ought to make a purposeful and conscious effort to study the language with or without an instructor.

3. The students must understand audio materials, hence he or she should hear the right pronunciation of words and sounds.

Analyzing and doing a survey about the afore-said first four biggest obstacles to learning English as a second language, it turns out that the biggest challenge is linked to lack of commitment to learning a language. The second biggest problem is because of poor learning environments. Then it is followed by unqualified teachers who approach the teaching process frivolously. The last and the least percentage of poor language learning is related to inadequate materials that are offered to the students during the school year.

The following graph charts illustrate the relevant percents according to the survey in society:

1. Inadequate learning materials -10%
2. Unqualified teachers -24%
3. Weak learning environment-30%
4. Lack of commitment to learning-36%

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